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EFFECT OF ZINC SUBSTITUTION ON MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF NICKEL FERRITE NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

Zinc substituted nickel ($Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$ with $x=0.00, 0.2$ and 0.4) ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel auto combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. The metal nitrate to fuel ratio was taken as 1:3. The as synthesized powder of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles is annealed at $600^\circ C$ for 6h and prepared sample was used for characterization and investigations of structural and magnetic properties. The structural characterization of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles were done by X-ray diffraction technique. The crystallite size obtained by Scherrer's formula is in the order of 24-29 nm. The lattice constant determined from XRD data is in the reported range 8.329-8.378 Å. The magnetic properties were investigated at room temperature using pulse field hysteresis loop tracer technique. The magnetic behaviour of Ni-Zn spinel ferrite nanoparticles suggests that the zinc strongly influences the magnetic properties.

Keywords: Ni-Zn ferrite, Sol-gel auto-combustion, Nanoparticles, XRD, Magnetic properties

Introduction

Ferrites are ferrimagnetic oxides consisting of ferric oxide and metal oxides. On the basis of crystal structure ferrites are grouped into three classes namely garnet, spinel and hexagonal ferrite. The spinel ferrites are widely studied because of their superior properties such as structural, magnetic, electrical and catalytic properties, all of which are different from those of their bulk counterparts and applications point of view in various and new fields like magnetic drug delivery, catalyst, sensors, biological, biomedical and medical science [1-4]. The spinel ferrite has the general formula of MFe_2O_4 where M is a divalent metal ion (Mn, Co, Ni, and Zn

etc.). Among spinel ferrites, Zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4) has normal spinel structure and promising magnetic material for high-density recording applications because of their high magneto crystalline anisotropy, high coercivity, moderate saturation magnetization and high chemical and structural stability at higher temperatures, which make it a good candidate for the electronic components used in computers, recording devices, and magnetic cards [5-9]. The properties of nanoparticles mostly depend on synthesis method therefore nowadays different synthesis methods are being used for synthesis nanomaterials. The nickel spinel ferrite has an inverse spinel structure. Nickel ferrite possess high electrical resistivity, high saturation magnetization, and is a good candidate for high frequency applications as well as magnetic data storage. Ni-Zn spinel ferrite nanoparticles have been synthesized using various methods, such as co-precipitation method, hydrothermal method, micro emulsion method, sol-gel method, sonochemical reaction method, ball milling, laser ablation and aerosol method [10-14]. Among synthesis methods, sol-gel auto combustion method has been used for synthesis of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles. Auto-combustion synthesis process is based upon the thermo-chemical concept used in the field of propellants and explosives, its extrapolation to the combustion synthesis of nano-oxides. A various fuels have been used in the combustion synthesis of ferrite nonmaterial, like glycine, urea, hydrazine, citric acid, and sucrose. All these fuels serve two purposes: (i) they are the source of C and H, the reducing elements, which form CO_2 and H_2O on combustion and liberate heat; and (ii) they form complexes with the metal ions facilitating homogeneous mixing of the cations in solution. The exothermicity of the redox reaction ranges from 1200 K to 1800 K. The nature of combustion differs from flaming to non-flaming depending upon which fuel used for preparation of nano-material. In the present work citric acid has been used to prepare Zinc ferrite nanoparticles. The present research report deals with the synthesis of zinc substituted nickel ferrite nanoparticles by sol-gel auto combustion method using citric acid as fuel and to investigate the structural and magnetic properties of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles as a function of zinc substitution. In the literature, structural and electrical properties of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles are reported, but systematic investigation of their magnetic behaviour as a function of zinc substitution is not studied.

Experimental

Material and Synthesis

The $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Zn}_x\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ with $x=0.0, 0.2,$ and 0.4 nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. The metal nitrates to fuel ratio was taken as 1:3. All the reagents used for the synthesis of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles were analytical grade and used as received without further purification. The stoichiometric proportion of Zinc nitrate $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, zinc nitrate $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ferric nitrate $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and citric acid $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ were separately dissolved in minimum amount of distilled water using magnetic stirrer. After complete dissolution of metal nitrates in distilled water then nickel nitrate, zinc nitrate and ferric nitrate solution were mixed together and stirred sometime with constant heating at 90°C . After some stirring citric acid solution was added to the nitrates solution. The all solution was again stirred for about 6h at 90°C on a hot plate with continuous stirring until it becomes viscous and finally formed a very viscous gel. The temperature is further raised up to 120°C so that the ignition of the gel suddenly starts. The dried gel was subsequently swelling into foam like and undergoes a strong self-propagating combustion reaction to give a loose Ni-Zn ferrite nano-powder. Finally the as prepared loose Ni-Zn ferrite powder was grinded for 30 min and annealed at 600°C temperature for 4h in muffle furnace to improve the ordering and for further characterization.

Characterization

The crystalline phase of the prepared Zinc ferrite sample was identified by X-ray diffraction technique using XPERT-PRO system. X-ray powder diffractions were performed at room temperature using monochromatic Cu-K_α radiation with $\lambda=1.54060 \text{ \AA}$ operated at 40kV and 35mA with 2θ ranging from 20° to 80° at a step size 0.02° per second. The magnetic measurements were carried out through pulse field hysteresis loop tracer technique at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

XRD analysis

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of the annealed Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks observed at $2\theta= 30.32^\circ, 35.65^\circ, 43.33^\circ, 53.67^\circ, 57.24^\circ, 62.80^\circ$ corresponding to the (220), (311), (400), (422), (511) and (440) planes, respectively. In this XRD pattern other oxides or impurity

phases are not detected therefore XRD patterns confirm the formation of cubic spinel type lattice of ZnFe_2O_4 , which matches well with the standard XRD pattern. The lattice constant (a) of Ni-Zn ferrite samples were obtained from the following equation

$$a = d\sqrt{(h^2+k^2+l^2)} \quad \text{\AA} \quad (1)$$

Where, (h k l) are the Miller Indices, d is inter planner spacing. Thus, lattice constant was computed using the d value and the (h k l) parameters. The crystallite size (D) has been calculated from FWHM (full width at half maximum) of most intense peak (311) data using Debye-Scherrer's equation [15].

$$D = \frac{(0.9\lambda)}{(\beta \cos \theta)} \quad \text{nm} \quad (2)$$

Where, D is the crystallite size, λ is the wavelength of Cu-K α (1.5405 \AA), β is the full width at half maxima of the most intense diffraction peaks and θ is the Bragg's angle. The reflection from (311) plane was used for determination of average crystallite size.

Figure 1. A typical X-ray diffraction pattern of NiFe_2O_4 nanoparticles

The volume (V) of the unit cell was calculated by using the following equation;

$$V = a^3 \quad [A] \quad (3)$$

Where, V is the volume of unit cell, 'a' is the lattice constant. The X-Ray density (ρ_b) of the sample was calculated using the relation given by Smit and Wijn following formula [16].

$$\rho_b = \frac{8M}{N_A a^3} \text{ gm/cm}^3 \quad (4)$$

Where, M is the molecular weight and N_A is the Avogadro's number and 'a' is the lattice parameter. The bulk density (ρ_m) of Zinc ferrite sample was determined using standard formula.

$$\rho_m = \frac{m}{\pi r^2 t} \text{ gm/cm}^3 \quad (5)$$

Where m is mass of pellets, r is the radius of pellets and t is thickness of pellet. Porosity (P %) of the $ZnFe_2O_4$ sample was calculated from X-ray density and bulk density.

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_b} \right) \times 100 \% \quad (6)$$

Where, ρ_b is the X-ray density and ρ_m is the bulk density. The structural parameters such as lattice constant, unit cell volume, X-ray density, bulk density, porosity and specific surface area of N-Zn ferrite nano particles are given in Table 1. From table 1, it was understood that the calculated values of lattice constant of Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles is 8.329Å which agree with the reported values [17]. The crystallite size of the Zinc ferrite nanoparticles is 26 nm. The X-ray density is found to be of the order of 5.301gm/cm³. The bulk density of Zinc ferrite nano particles was measured from the standard formula [18].

Table 1. Lattice constant, volume of unit cell, X-ray density, bulk density, porosity and crystallite size from XRD data.

Structural Parameters	X=0.0	X=0.20	X=0.40
Lattice constant (a)	8.329 Å	8.336 Å	8.342 Å
Volume of unit cell (V)	577.80 Å ³	579.26 Å ³	580.51 Å ³
X-Ray density (ρ _x)	5.379 (gm/cm ³)	5.411 (gm/cm ³)	5.446 (gm/cm ³)
Crystallite Size(t)	22.00 nm	25 nm	29 nm

Magnetic Properties

The magnetic properties of zinc substituted nickel spinel ferrite nano particles were carried out by using pulse field hysteresis loop tracer technique. The magnetic parameters such as saturation magnetization, remanence magnetization and coercivity were obtained from the M-H loops. The values of all these magnetic parameters obtained from M-H plots are listed in table 2. It can be observed from table 2 that the saturation magnetization initially increases from x=0.00 to 0.2 and then decreases for x=0.4. This typical behavior of magnetization is due to substitution of non-magnetic zinc ions in place of magnetic nickel ions.

Parameters	X=0.00	X=0.20	X=0.40	
Saturation magnetization	70.16 (emu/gm)	72.45 (emu/gm)	67.76 (emu/gm)	
Magneton number	Calculated	2.853	2.896	2.935
	Observed	2.940	3.062	2.888

Applying Neel’s model of ferrimagnetism we can obtain Neel’s magnetic moment given by the relation

$$\eta_{B(\text{Neel})} = M_B - M_A \quad (6)$$

Where, M_B and M_A denotes magnetic moment of B-site ions and A-site ions respectively. The calculated values of Neel's magnetic moment are given in table 2. For calculating Neel's magnetic moment it was assumed that zinc ions occupy tetrahedral sites, nickel has strong preference towards B-site while ferric ions occupy both tetrahedral and octahedral sites. It is observed from table 2 that observed and calculated magneton number fairly agree with each other for $x=0.00$ and 0.2 but it shows deviation for $x=0.4$. This indicates that for $x>0.2$ structure is non-collinear and for $x\leq 0.2$ the structure is collinear. Thus, the experimental results on magnetic measurements suggest that zinc ion strongly influence the magnetic properties of nickel ferrite. Similar, behavior was also reported in the literature [21].

Conclusions-

Ni-Zn ferrite nanoparticles of nano size have been synthesized successfully by sol-gel auto combustion method. X-ray diffraction pattern confirms the formation of cubic spinel structure in single phase without any impurity peak. The average crystallite size is obtained was of the order 26 nm. The lattice constant and other structural parameter are in the reported range. The saturation magnetization initially increases and then decreases. The structure is collinear up to $x=0.2$ beyond $x=0.2$ it becomes non-collinear. Thus, zinc substitution affects the magnetic properties of nickel ferrite.

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